

TRADE COOPERATION BETWEEN BUKHARA AND GERMANY (1920-1960)

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Annotation: From the first days of the founding of the People's Soviet Republic of Bukhara, it entered into diplomatic, economic and cultural relations with Eastern countries. However, these countries, which were ruled by monarchies in the past, were almost no different from the level of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic in terms of their development. That is why the progressive forces of the republic under the leadership of the head of the government F. Khojaev tried to connect with the countries that are at the stages of modern development in the economic, scientific and technical spheres.

Key words: Bukhara, F. Khojaev, Mukomil Burkhanov, Germany-Black Sea

But the historical situation at that time did not allow establishing cooperative relations with Western European countries and countries like the USA. There were specific reasons for this. The need to establish economic relations between Germany, which was defeated in the First World War in 1914-1918, was not a coincidence at that time. Meanwhile, the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic also tried to establish independent economic relations with countries like Germany.

It is known from sources that in order to establish economic and trade relations between the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic and Germany, the government of Bukhara used the mediation of Olimjon Idrisi, a representative of the Tatar nation living in Germany, Amin Suleiman, a millionaire of his time, and Eidelman, a Jewish merchant from Bukhara. In particular, Mukomil Burkhanov, the treasurer of the "Milliy Ittihad" organization, who was a close friend of F. Khojaev, kept the gold reserves of this organization. He was constantly traveling between the two countries to establish cooperation between Bukhara and Germany.

However, the economic and trade relations of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic and even the cultural cooperation were carried out through the RSFSR. This limited the possibility of establishing relations. The Soviet government established strict control over the Bukhara representative office in Moscow. Nevertheless, the People's Soviet Republic of Bukhara has taken practical steps to establish commercial relations with the German state and to continue this cooperation in a continuous perspective. A 5-story building was purchased for the purpose of commercial work on Barbarossa Street in Berlin at the expense of foreign exchange funds in Germany.

The government of Bukhara intended to organize an international exhibition by placing goldsmithing, jewelry, tailoring and other national art items here, and in this way, to raise the commercial relations between the two countries to a new level. Although diplomatic and political relations have not been established between the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic and Germany, some good things have been done in the field of economic and trade cooperation.

Companies of German industrialists such as "Germany-Black Sea", "Schroeder and its partners", "Sinkup" and "Russian-German Trade Organization" are in the process of establishing trade relations with the Republic of Bukhara. After receiving offers from countries like Germany, a "State Trade Office" was established in September 1922 and began to operate on an independent "self-financing" basis. "100,000 pounds of cotton, 100,000 pounds of sweet brain, 50,000 pieces of black leather, and about 10,000 pounds of wool" collected by the former trading branch were brought to the market for sale.

Most of these products were sent to Moscow, Nizhny Novgorod and Makar fairs for sale and for recommendation to foreign merchants. Naturally, German businessmen who had branches of trade and industrial companies in various cities of Soviet Russia were interested in Bukhara goods. In 1922, summer fairs were opened in Leipzig (Germany) and Lyon (France). 14,000 items were sold at the Leipzig fair. In particular, Soviet Russia brought raw materials and wood products to the market. Bukhara goods also gained fame at fairs in German cities. "Lyon fair is much bigger than last year (1921). Things put in by Russia have had a lot of success.

"Everyone's encouragement was necessary," writes "Bukhara Akhbori" newspaper.

German merchants expressed their desire and desire to buy black leather, cotton, silk, silk products, licorice medicinal plant and wool among the goods available in the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic. In the summer of 1922, a special appeal was received from the German government to the representative of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic in Moscow. In it, the German government turned to Bukhara's representative in Moscow and asked for red gold or black leather in exchange for factory machines and other things.

Taking advantage of the opportunity to establish trade relations with Germany, the government of Bukhara sent a private trade delegation headed by Mirza Abdulkadir Muhiddinov to Moscow in July 1922 to meet with German representatives. In the capital of Soviet Russia, a tripartite negotiation was held between Fronstein, A. Muhiddinov, head of the "Eastern branch" of the People's

Inspectorate of the RSFSR, and representatives of foreign trade (Germany). It seems that the negotiations ended with the success of the representatives of Bukhara, in one of the reports: "Comrade M. Muhiddinov bought 40,000 blackbuck skins to the Latvian ambassador with the condition that they will be exported abroad (to Germany). This sale was approved by the Bukhara Council of Supervisors.

Bukhara Karakoli is the biggest wealth of the republic, it has played an important role in livestock breeding, and since ancient times it has made up 4/1 of the products exported abroad. In the sources, it is noted that cattle breeding was more developed among the nomadic herdsmen Turkmen who lived on the Bukhara-Afghan border, and they account for almost half of the cattle skins produced.

Trade in karakol skins was carried out by the "German karakol company", which had dozens of stores in German cities selling Bukhara karakol skins through Russia during the Emirate period. But due to the Russian civil war of 1918-1920 and foreign intervention, and before that, the First World War, trade in black leather was almost stopped.

As a result, Bukhara herdsmen, who were growing 2 million pieces of black leather annually, were deprived of the opportunity to profit from this industry, and even in 1920, black leather production fell to 200,000 pieces. In the spring of 1921, due to the New Economic Policy in Soviet Russia, market relations developed, and the demand for the products of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic increased. At one time, foreign businessmen who were trading at Russian fairs also began to look at Bukhara products with interest. In 1922, the number of blackbirds reached 800,000. The government of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic had the task of paving the way for the development of the cattle-breeding industry, eliminating the obstacles that harm economic growth, ending abnormal situations, and reducing customs duties. Since 1923, the government has taken a serious look at this issue and re-established the "Karakol trade and industry" company. A duty of 10 gold soums was imposed on each pood (16 kg) of blackbuck skin. Karakol trade was taken from voluntary, private traders and given to state and cooperative companies.

The position of the "Karakol trade and industry" company increased, and a large amount of karakol skins were exported to Germany. In one of the reports: "There is no doubt that the prices of cotton and black leather goods, which have fallen in Bukhara, are being sold to Russia and abroad (Germany), and the economic situation of farmers and herders who prepare and sell these goods

should improve to some extent. The fact that the price of black leather and cotton is 9-10 soums in Bukhara today should give hope to traders and farmers.

The trading process at the Makar and Irbit fairs of Russia started on the first day of August in 1922-1923 and lasted for 1.5 months. German merchants who visited these fairs bought mainly cotton and black leather from Bukhara merchants. The government of the Republic of Bukhara, using these fairs, opened the way to foreign trade and gained the opportunity to sell accumulated products (cow skin, cotton, leather, wool). In 1922-1923, a separate bank was opened in the republic to help companies and private merchants, and its annual turnover was 100 billion soums.

The merchants of Bukhara used to buy necessary goods for the needs of the republic from the fairs. "7,000 buckets of cement, 8 wagons of plywood, 48,000 arshins (measurement of length) of various chits, 1,000 school tetrads (notebooks) and equipment imported from Germany were purchased from the Makar fair. According to reports in "Bukhara Akhbori" newspaper, Russian and foreign (German) goods purchased from seasonal fairs in Russian cities were brought to Chorjoi by steamer. Then it was distributed throughout the regions of Bukhara.

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